

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Assessment of the resource of elements of transportation machines operated in mining energy enterprises

To cite this article: A M Umirzokov *et al* 2022 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* **990** 012063

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Study on the Influence of Isolated Roughness on Hypersonic Flow over Blunt Wedge](#)
Xiaojun Tang, Jingzhen Han, Mingfang Shi et al.
- [Electrolytic Refining of Rare Earth Element from Neodymium Magnet Using Molten Salt](#)
Yuki Kamimoto, Masaki Wakita and Ryoichi Ichino
- [Two-point method uncertainty during control and measurement of cylindrical element diameters](#)
V I Glukhov, V V Shalay and H. Radev

Assessment of the resource of elements of transportation machines operated in mining energy enterprises

A M Umirzokov¹, M A Abdullo¹, F I Jobirov¹, S S Saidullozoda^{1,2} and A B Tashripov¹

¹ Tajik Technical University named after M S Osimi, 11, academicians of the Radjabovs, Dushanbe 734042, The Republic of Tajikistan

² South Ural State University, 76, Lenin Avenue, Chelyabinsk 454080, Russian Federation

E-mail: saivali.saidullo@mail.ru

Abstract. In mining energy enterprises located at altitudes over 1000 meters above sea level, transport machines are operated in harsh road-climatic conditions, contributing to accelerated wear of equipment and machinery elements. The purpose of the study is related to the assessment and adjustment of the resource of the elements of transport machines operated in mining energy enterprises. The work is devoted to the assessment of the intensity of wear of the elements of machines involved in the transportation of rocks, taking into account the influence of the most significant factors. To assess the resource of elements of transport machines operated in mining energy enterprises, a complex scientific approach was used, taking into account the influence of various combinations of significant factors. The practical significance of the work is associated with planning the need for elements of transport machines operated in mining energy enterprises. The research results, including the simplified mathematical model presented in the article, can be recommended for assessing and adjusting the resource of the elements of transport machines operated in mining energy enterprises.

1. Introduction

In the erecting of mining energy enterprises, a significant amount of work falls on transport vehicles, the most popular of which are mining dump trucks. The only elements of car in contact with the road is the vehicles tire. At the same time, a vehicles tire is considered the most vulnerable element of mining dump trucks, the formation of the resource of which is due to a sufficient number of significant and insignificant factors.

The significance of the factors affecting the formation of the tire resource of transport machines in mining energy enterprises is justified by on the results of theoretical studies based on the assumptions that the main significant factors are road and climatic conditions, as well as the vertical load applied to the wheels of the car.

On the basis of a priori reasoning, it has been established that the mining energy enterprises operating transport machines are characterizes by the following features:

- The resource of tires of transport machines in mining energy enterprises differs significantly from the standard resource established by the manufacturer, and the wear intensity of the tread

pattern is high. There is also a frequent decommissioning of truck tires due to mechanical damage that cannot be restored;

- Under these conditions, such factors as height above sea level, driver reliability, vehicles speed (in conditions of Rogun hydro power plants (HPP) construction, the average speed of transport machines per trip is small and amounts to about 11 ... 20 km/h), type of loading, etc. belong to the category of insignificant factors. Consequently, in the process of experimental studies, the influence of these factors was not taken into account.

2. Materials and research methods

During the operation of transport machines in difficult mining energy enterprises, the resource of a vehicles tire, one way or another, is influenced by more than forty factors that are characterized by inconstancy and vary within a wide range [1]. Moreover, the combination of the influence of a wide variety of factors that determine where, and hence the service life of a tire, is also variable and refers to an event that has a probabilistic nature with a wide range of values of numerical indicators [2-4]. It can be assumed that when assessing and adjusting the resource of tires of transport machines, it is impossible to take into account the influence of each of these factors separately [5]. For this purpose, road and climatic conditions and vertica load can be singled out as the most significant factors determining the formation of the resource of tires of transport machines. Then a simplified mathematical model for correcting the resource of transport machines in mining energy enterprises (for example, the construction of the Rogun HPP) L_t^c can be expressed by the following relationship:

$$L_t^c = L_t^s \cdot k_D \cdot k_t \cdot k_l \cdot k_{ot} = L_t^s \cdot (1 - k_d) \cdot k_t \cdot k_l \cdot k_{ot}, \quad (1)$$

where, L_t^s standard resource of tires of transport machines under normal operating conditions, thousand km (for tires of standard size 18.00-25 $L_t^s = 45$ thousand km); $k_D = (1 - k_d)$ generalizing dynamic coefficient of tire life correction; k_d dynamic coefficient of road conditions; k_t a correction factor for the influence environment temperature on the formation of the tire life; k_l a correction factor for the influence of the vertica load on the formation of the tire life; k_{ot} a correction factor that takes into account the influence of other factors on the formation of tire life.

The value of the correction factor is determined by taking into account the average value of the vertica load acting on an individual tire P_t^{av}

$$P_t^{av} = \frac{\sum P}{n_k} \cdot \eta, \quad (2)$$

where, $\sum P$ the total value of the vertica load transmitted from the car to the road canvas using the tire, N; η the coefficient of distribution of the weight of the car along with the axles; n_k many car wheels on each axle, pieces.

The total value of the vertica load $\sum P$ transmitted from trucks, cement trucks, fuel trucks and similar trucks to the road canvas can be determined from the expression

$$\sum P = (m_c + \frac{m_w}{2}) \cdot g \cdot \eta, \quad (3)$$

where, m_c curb weight of the car, kg; m_w weight of cargo, kg; g acceleration of gravity, m/s^2 .

Based on the put forward theoretical assumptions that fluctuations of significant external influences obey the normal distribution law, the results of experimental studies were processed by the methods of mathematical statistics [6]. In the process of experimental studies, the main probabilistic and statistical

characteristics of external influences were determined, which determine the resource of truck tires in real operating conditions (figures 1 and 2).

At the same time, according to the results of experimental studies, the main probabilistic and statistical characteristics of significant factors that form the tire life were determined: road conditions, tire temperature, relative vertical load, as well as the wear intensity of the tread pattern of tires installed on BelAZ-7540B, SHACMAN-SX3256DR384, HOWO-336 and Dongfeng-DFL3251A dump trucks.

The empirical distributions were compared with the theoretical ones using the Pearson χ^2 goodness test [7]. The calculation results show that the empirical characteristics of the distribution of factors are in good agreement with the theoretical normal distribution law. The probabilities of agreement of the distributions of external influences $P(\chi^2)$ were in the range of 0.32...0.83.

Figure 1. Graphs of empirical and theoretical distributions of the resource allocation functions for tires of standard size 18.00 -25, mounted on BelAZ-7540B dump trucks, operated during the construction of the Rogun HPP: $L_{av} = 25.14$ thousand km; $\sigma = 4.05$ thousand km; $\nu = 16\%$.

Figure 2. Graphs of empirical and theoretical distributions of resource allocation functions for tires of 12.00-20 standard size mounted on SHACMAN-SX3256DR384, HOWO-336 and Dongfeng-DFL3251A dump trucks, operated under the conditions of Rogun HPP construction: $L_{av} = 32.2$ thousand km; $\sigma = 4.1$ thousand km; $\nu = 12.7\%$.

For these parameters, the following were determined: mathematical expectations, standard deviations, variances, coefficients of variation, as well as spectral densities.

The dynamics of the processes of forming the resource of tires of transport machines is most fully manifested like the course of their correlation functions and spectral densities. Spectral densities of external influences are additional estimates characterizing their dynamics in the frequency domain.

The distribution of the average resource value by months of the year, as well as the results of the spectral analysis of the wear process of tires of 18.00-25 standard size of BelAZ-7540B dump trucks, operated under the conditions of the Rogun HPP construction, are shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Distribution of the average value of the resource of tires of standard sizes 18.00-25 BelAZ-7540B dump trucks, operated in conditions of construction of the Rogun HPP by months of the year: 1 - an average monthly resource of tires before their decommissioning; 2 - spectral densities of tire resource distribution; 3 - boundaries of the tire resource allocation spectra.

As can be seen from the graph, the boundaries of the resource distribution spectra of the tires of BelAZ-7540B dump trucks, operated under conditions, vary within a wide range. In this case, the lower, upper and average values of the boundaries of the tire resource spectrum, respectively, are $L_{min} = 8.2$ thousand km, $L_{max} = 41.8$ thousand km, $L_{av} = 24.9$ thousand km. Tire resources by months of the year are distributed mainly according to the normal law with coefficients of variation $v = 6.0 \dots 41.2\%$.

The distribution of the average tire life by months of the year, as well as the results of the spectral analysis of the wear process of tires of standard size 12.00-20, mounted on trucks of the Chinese production SHACMAN-SX3256DR384, HOWO-336 and Dongfeng-DFL3251A, operated under the conditions of the Rogun HPP construction, are shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. Distribution of the average value of the resource of tires of standard sizes 12.00-20 for SHACMAN-SX3256DR384, HOWO-336 and Dongfeng-DFL3251A dump trucks, operated under the conditions of the Rogun HPP construction by months of the year: 1 - average monthly tire life before taking them out of service; 2 - spectral densities of tire resource distribution; 3 - boundaries of the tire resource allocation spectra.

As can be seen from the graph, the boundaries of the resource distribution spectra of the tires of SHACMAN-SX3256DR384, HOWO-336 and Dongfeng-DFL3251A dump trucks operated in mining energy enterprises vary within a wide range.

In this case, the lower, upper and average values of the boundaries of the tire resource spectrum, respectively, are $L_{min} = 16.1$ thousand km, $L_{max} = 50.0$ thousand km, $L_{av} = 32.1$ thousand km. Tire resources by months of the year are distributed mainly according to the normal law with coefficients of variation $v = 6.4 \dots 42.3\%$.

3. Research results and discussion

In real operating conditions of transport machines, in most cases, there is a complex or simultaneous influence of many factors that determine their resource [8].

Let us consider the joint influence of the most significant factors on the formation of the resource of a vehicles tire.

The combined effect of road conditions and vertical load on the wear intensity of the tread pattern, and, consequently, on the resource of tires of transport machines under the conditions of the Rogun HPP construction at a conditionally constant tire surface temperature is shown in figure 5.

It can be seen from the analysis above graph that the greatest influence on the formation of the resource of tires of transport machines in the conditions of the Rogun HPP construction is exerted by road conditions, which are characterized by the roughness road canvas, which varies in the aisles from 6.0 to 8.0 m/km and above.

An equally important combination of factors that determine the wear intensity of the tread pattern or the resource of tires of transport machines is the joint influence of the roughness road and the temperature tire surface [9; 10].

It should be noted that the influence of the rough road on the formation of the tire's resource is aggravated by an increase in the temperature of its surface. It has been experimentally established that for the conditions of the Rogun HPP construction, in the summer period of vehicle operation, the tire surface temperature often reaches 80°C and higher. At the same time, the temperature difference between the tire surface and the ambient air varies in the range of 45 ... 55°C.

The dependence of the wear intensity of the tread pattern of tires of standard size 18.00-25 for operating conditions in mining energy enterprises (for example, the construction of the Rogun HPP) is shown in figure 6.

Figure 5. Dependence of the wear I intensity of the tire tread pattern standard size 18.00 -25 from vertical load G and roughness road N .

Figure 6. Dependence of the wear I intensity of the tread pattern of a tire of standard size 18.00-25 on the roughness road N and tire temperature T .

From the analysis of the above graph, it follows that under the combined influence of road conditions and the temperature of the tire surface, the wear intensity of the tread pattern is noticeably increased. The influence of the complexity of road conditions, determined, in our case, by the roughness of road canvas increases significantly with an increase in tire temperature due to a decrease in the mechanical properties of rubber and a deterioration in its structural performance.

Approximately the same effect is observed when vertical load and tire surface temperature are combined. The dependence of the combined influence of vertical load and tire surface temperature under the same road conditions is shown in figure 7.

Figure 7. Dependence of the wear I intensity of the tire tread pattern standard size 18.00 -25 from vertical load G and tire temperature T .

Experimental data on the combined influence of these factors were obtained under the conditions of one driving route with the maximum possible variations in the vertical load (gross car mass) and tire surface temperature. In this case, the surface temperature of the tire, as in previous experiments, varied within the aisles of 50 ... 80°C, and the gross mass car was 45 ... 57 tons for BelAZ-7540B trucks.

4. Conclusions

Based on the study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Of the whole variety of factors that form the resource of tires of transport machines in the conditions of the Rogun HPP construction, the most significant are road conditions; tire surface temperature; vertical load applied to the wheels car. All rest insignificant factors are combined into a single factor, referred to as other factors. The significance of factors affecting the resource of tires of transport machines was established according to the recommendations of E.S. Kuznetsov based on a multifactorial mathematical model.

2. Based on the results of experimental studies, the main probabilistic and statistical characteristics of significant factors that form the tire life were determined. It was found that the resource of tires of transport machines are distributed according to the normal law and are characterized by the following indicators:

- For tires of standard sizes 18.00-25: $L_{av} = 25.14$ thousand km; $\sigma = 4.05$ thousand km; $\nu = 16.00\%$;
- For tires of standard sizes 12.00-20: $L_{av} = 32.2$ thousand km; $\sigma = 4.1$ thousand km; $\nu = 12.7\%$.

References

- [1] Goryunov S V 2013 Functional model for predicting the durability of tires of career dump trucks. *Journal "Izvestiya MGTU "MAMI"* **2(16)** 149-154
- [2] Tursunov A A 2003 *Managing the performance of vehicles in mountainous operating conditions* (Dushanbe: Irfon) 356
- [3] Umirzokov A M, Saibov A A, Jobirov F I, Abaev A Kh and Berdiev A L 2018 Classification of factors affecting tire mileage in high-mountain quarries. *Politekhnicheskiy Vestnik. Series: Engineering Research* **3(43)** 44-48
- [4] Umirzokov A M, Mallaboev U M, Saidullozoda S S and Khabibullozoda Kh Kh 2020 Classification of factors influencing the reliability of the driver-vehicle-road-environment (DVRE) system in the conditions of mountain quarries. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* **817** 012036

- [5] Bakeev R B 2001 The problem of determining and adjusting the standards for the resource of automobile tires. *Problems of the operation of cars, construction, road and lifting-transport machines: Interuniversity collection of scientific papers. Tyumen* 3-5
- [6] Umirzokov A M, Saibov A A, Abaev A Kh, Berdiev A L and Jobirov F I 2018 Probabilistic-statistical assessment of the influence of factors affecting the mileage of automobile tires in the conditions of alpine quarries. *Politekhicheskiy Vestnik. Series: Engineering Research* **3(43)** 40-44
- [7] Gafarova L M, Zavyalova I G and Mustafin N N 2015 On the peculiarities of applying the Pearson χ^2 criterion of agreement. *Economic and social-humanitarian research* **4(8)** 63-67
- [8] Shchekochikhin A V 2015 Factors affecting the resource of tires during operation. *Priority scientific directions: from theory to practice* **17** 120-124
- [9] Kadyrov A S, Kabikenov S Zh, Zharkenov N B and Nurmaganbet N S 2015 Methodology for determining the predicted resource of automobile tires of heavy-duty dump trucks by operational indicators. *Success of modern natural science* **1-4** 648-650
- [10] Goryunov S V and Sharipov V M 2015 Prediction of the durability of pneumatic tires of dump trucks. *Mining information and analytical bulletin (scientific and technical journal)* **11** 127-130